

Synthesis, spectral characterization and antifungal studies on lanthanum(III) and praseodymium(III) complexes with Schiff bases derived from 2,6-diacetylpyridine and 4-amino-3-(phenyl/substituted phenyl)-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles

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Abstract : In the present communication eight new lanthanum(III) and praseodymium(III) complexes of the general formula $[\text{LnCl}(\text{L})(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$ ($\text{Ln} = \text{La}^{\text{III}}$ and Pr^{III} ; $\text{LH}_2 =$ Schiff bases derived from 2,6-diacetylpyridine and 4-amino-3-(phenyl/2-chlorophenyl/4-chlorophenyl/4-nitrophenyl)-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles) were synthesized in the presence of base. The complexes have been characterized by elemental analyses, electrical conductance, magnetic susceptibility, electronic absorption, infrared, far-infrared, ^1H NMR spectral studies. The thermal behaviour of the complex under non-isothermal condition was investigated by TGA techniques. The presence of coordinated water molecule in the complex was inferred from TG which indicates the loss of one water molecule at 150–165 °C. All these Schiff bases and their complexes have also been screened for their antifungal activities by MIC method.

Keywords : Synthesis, La^{III} , Pr^{III} , Schiff bases, spectral, antifungal.

Introduction

There has been considerable development in the chemistry of transition metal complexes with heterocyclic thione/thiol donors^{1–9}. 1,2,4-Triazoles and their derivatives are associated with various biological activities, such as anti-convulsant, antifungal, anticancer, anti-inflammatory and antibacterial properties. Several compounds containing 1,2,4-triazole ring are well known for drugs. 1,2,4-Triazoles containing amino group are also of importance for obtaining various Schiff bases with well known antimicrobial properties. These diversified applications are at least in part a consequence of the numerous approaches that are available for the insertion of specific functionalities into the 1,2,4-triazole nucleus. The alteration in chemical structure of substituted 1,2,4-triazoles strongly change their activities and affect their interaction with cells and tissues, thereby leading to different biological effects. However, studies on coordination behaviour of such ligands are very limited. The coordination behaviour of

such ligands depends upon the nature of metal ion, nature of the substituent on the ligands and the pH of the medium. Patil *et al.*¹⁰ reported the coordination behaviour of 1,2,4-triazole Schiff bases towards lanthanum(III).

In this present study, we report the synthetic, structural aspects and antimicrobial properties of lanthanum(III) and praseodymium(III) with Schiff bases derived from 2,6-diacetylpyridine and 4-amino-3-(phenyl/2-chlorophenyl/4-chlorophenyl/4-nitrophenyl)-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles. As per my knowledge no report on this topic is available so far.

Experimental

General information :

The solvents were purchased from Merck and used without further purification. Lanthanum(III) and praseodymium(III) chlorides were purchased from B.D.H. The ligands were prepared as reported in literature. Melting points were determined on a Buchi 530 apparatus in

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open capillary tubes. IR spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu 8201 PC model FT IR spectrophotometer as KBr disks. ^1H NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker DRX-300 spectrometer using $\text{DMSO-}d_6$ as solvent. Chemical shifts (δ) are reported in parts per million (ppm) relative to an internal standard of Me_4Si . A Hitachi Japan model U-2000 spectrophotometer was used to record the electronic spectra. Elemental analyses were recorded by Elementar Vario EL III Carlo Erba 1108 models. Elemental analysis (C, H, N, M) indicates that the found and calculated values were within acceptable limits (± 0.5). Molar conductance of 10^{-3} M solutions of the complexes in DMSO was recorded on a Hanna EC 215 conductivity meter by using 0.01 M KCl water solution as calibrate. The purity of compounds was checked by thin layer chromatography on silica gel plate using ether and ethyl acetate as a solvent system. Iodine chamber was used as a developing chamber.

Procedure for biological activity study :

In vitro antibacterial and antifungal activity :

All newly prepared Schiff bases and their complexes were screened for their activity against four fungal organisms *Colletrotricum falcatum*, *Fusarium oxysporium* and *Curvularia lunata* and four bacteria namely *Bacillus subtilis*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Streptococcus pyogenes* and *Salmonella typhi* by petri dishes method¹¹. Fungicidal and bactericidal activity of each compound was evaluated at three different concentrations, i.e. 10, 100 and 1000 ppm. For each compound 1% standard solution was prepared and 1 mL of the solution was diluted with 9 mL of the solvent (DMSO). Petri dishes of equal diameter were sterilised at 180 °C. Stock solutions of each compound were prepared for three concentration viz. 10, 100 and 1000 ppm. Solution of 1 mL of each concentration was poured in presterilised petri dishes and 9 mL of agar medium was added immediately. Each dish was rotated on the table top in order to achieve through mixing of medium with the compound. After this, fungus and bacterial strain was inoculated in the dishes (diameter 5 mm). These set were then inoculated at 30 ± 2 °C. The colony diameter of the test organism was measured with mm scale after 6 days. The percentage inhibition of the growth of the test organism was calculated by following formula.

$$\% \text{ Inhibition} = 100(\text{Cd} - \text{Td})/\text{Cd}$$

where Cd = Colony diameter of control and Td = Colony diameter of treated set.

Each set was kept in triplicate.

Minimum inhibitory concentrations :

The minimum inhibitory concentrations (MICs) in 1000, 100 and 10 ppm were noted. To ensure that solvent had no effect on fungal and bacterial growth, a control test was performed with test medium supplemented with DMSO at the same dilutions as used in the experiment. Fluconazole was used as a standard drug for antifungal and gentamycin was used as a standard drug for antibacterial activity.

Preparation of the complexes :

Two methods were adopted to synthesize lanthanum(III) and praseodymium(III) complexes :

- (a) *Microwave oven method* : A mixture of lanthanum(III) chloride or praseodymium(III) chloride in ethanol (*ca.* 5 cm³) and appropriate ligand in 1 : 1 molar ratio containing ethanolic solution of sodium hydroxide (*ca.* 3 cm³) was irradiated for *ca.* 10–15 min. The product was taken out of the oven, washed with ethanol and hot water and then dried *in vacuo*.
- (b) *Conventional thermal method* : To a solution of appropriate ligand (0.02 mol) in methanol (20 cm³), LnCl_3 (0.02 mol) in methanol (10 cm³) containing potassium hydroxide (0.04 mol) was added. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 10–22 h. Brown to orange colored precipitate was separated out which were filtered, washed with water followed by ethanol and dried *in vacuo*.

The details of the reactions along with the analytical data of the products are given in Tables 1(a) and 1(b).

Results and discussion

The condensation reactions of 2,6-diacetylpyridine with mercapto triazoles in anhydrous alcohol give rise to ligands, bis(Schiff bases) is shown in Scheme 1.

These ligands react with lanthanum(III) chloride or praseodymium(III) chloride under microwave or heating condition and in both cases products of type

Table 1(a). Reactions of lanthanum(III) and praseodymium(III) chloride with Schiff bases derived from 4-amino-3-(phenyl/substituted phenyl)-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles and 2,6-diacetylpyridine

Reactants	Molar ratio	Refluxing time (h)	Product	Color	Yield (%)	Decomp. temp. (°C)
LaCl ₃ + DPMTH ₂	1 : 1	15	[LaCl(DPMT)H ₂ O]	Brown	40	190
PrCl ₃ + DPMTH ₂	1 : 1	15	[PrCl(DPMT)H ₂ O]	Light brown	45	220
LaCl ₃ + DOCMTH ₂	1 : 1	10	[LaCl(DOCMT)H ₂ O]	Dark brown	45	240
PrCl ₃ + DOCMTH ₂	1 : 1	10	[PrCl(DOCMT)H ₂ O]	Cream	40	260
LaCl ₃ + DPCMTH ₂	1 : 1	10	[LaCl(DPCMT)H ₂ O]	Light brown	45	198
PrCl ₃ + DPCMTH ₂	1 : 1	15	[PrCl(DPCMT)H ₂ O]	Cream	43	215
LaCl ₃ + DNMTTH ₂	1 : 1	20	[LaCl(DNMT)H ₂ O]	Dark yellow	40	260
PrCl ₃ + DNMTTH ₂	1 : 1	22	[PrCl(DNMT)H ₂ O]	Orange	46	245

Table 1(b). Analytical data of lanthanum(III) and praseodymium(III) complexes with Schiff base derived from 4-amino-3-(phenyl/substituted phenyl)-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole and 2,6-diacetylpyridine

Complex	Molecular formula	Analyses (%) : Found (Calcd.)			
		C	H	N	Ln
[LaCl(DPMT)H ₂ O]	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ N ₈ OS ₂ ClLa	42.4 (42.6)	2.9 (3.1)	16.4 (16.5)	20.0 (20.5)
[PrCl(DPMT)H ₂ O]	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ N ₈ OS ₂ ClPr	42.4 (42.5)	2.9 (3.1)	16.4 (16.5)	20.4 (20.6)
[LaCl(DOCMT)H ₂]	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ N ₈ OS ₂ Cl ₃ La	38.5 (38.7)	2.3 (2.5)	14.9 (15.0)	18.4 (18.6)
[PrCl(DOCMT)H ₂ O]	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ N ₈ OS ₂ Cl ₃ Pr	37.9 (38.6)	2.3 (2.5)	14.8 (15.0)	18.5 (18.7)
[LaCl(DPCMT)H ₂ O]	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ N ₈ OS ₂ Cl ₃ La	38.5 (38.7)	2.4 (2.5)	14.7 (15.0)	18.4 (18.6)
[PrCl(DPCMT)H ₂ O]	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ N ₈ OS ₂ Cl ₃ Pr	38.4 (38.6)	2.3 (2.5)	14.0 (15.0)	18.5 (18.7)
[LaCl(DNMT)H ₂ O]	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ N ₁₀ O ₅ S ₂ ClLa	37.4 (37.6)	2.1 (2.5)	17.0 (18.2)	17.9 (18.1)
[PrCl(DNMT)H ₂ O]	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ N ₁₀ O ₅ S ₂ ClPr	37.3 (37.5)	2.2 (2.4)	18.1 (18.2)	18.0 (18.2)

Scheme 1. Structure of ligand.

{LnCl(L)(H₂O)} (Ln = La or Pr) have been isolated. The complexes are found to be soluble in nitrobenzene, DMF and DMSO. These complexes are non-conducting in nitrobenzene and decompose at higher temperature. The presence of water molecule has been inferred from thermogravimetric analysis, which shows weight loss at 150–165 °C corresponding to one water molecule.

Magnetic moments and electronic spectra :

The lanthanum(III) complexes, as expected, have no resultant magnetic moment, whereas the magnetic moment of praseodymium(III) complexes lie in the range of 3.58–3.61 μ_B , which shows little deviation from Van-Vleck value, i.e. 3.61 for the Pr³⁺ ion. The electronic

spectra of the paramagnetic lanthanide complexes have been the subject of recent extensive reviews¹², which deal particularly with the physical and theoretical aspects. The Pr^{3+} ion has the outer configuration $4f^2 5s^2 5p^6$ and follows the Russell-Saunders L, S, J coupling scheme with a certain amount of configuration interaction. The 5s and 5p subshell have a radial dispersion, which is greater than 4f electrons¹³, and, hence, shield the latter from the effect of coordinated ligands to a very large extent but not completely. Thus, the electronic spectra of Pr^{III} can be considered as derived from the spectra of the gaseous ions by a fairly small perturbation. The perturbation can be of two general types. The first is a general nephelauxetic effect owing to the drift of ligand or 5s, 5p electron density into the metal ion, slightly expanding the 4f subshell and reducing the 4f-4f interactions. The second is a crystal field splitting effect, which removes the degeneracy of the free ion levels and which can be represented with fair success by a point negative charge model having the appropriate molecular symmetry.

The spectra of La^{3+} ions are composed of closely spaced sharp lines. The group of lines is normally spread over an energy interval of several hundred cm^{-1} . These spectra arise from transitions among levels of f^n configuration. The 4f electrons of lanthanides are more or less protected from the influence of lattice by the polarization of $5s^2$ and $5p^6$ closed shell. The crystal field splitting effect in the La^{3+} ion is small, 200–300 cm^{-1} at the most. Thus, to a good approximation, the levels agree well with that for the free ion.

The f^2 configuration of a free Pr^{3+} ion involves 13 energy levels. Their location is found experimentally by the analyses of the spectra for a gaseous Pr^{3+} ion. The ground terms appears to be 3H_4 . The absorption spectra of Pr^{3+} ion solution in the visible region involve four bands due to the transition from the ground level to 3P_0 , $^3P_1 + ^1I_6$, 3P_0 and 1D_2 levels. The f - f transitions are weakly allowed due to some mixing of the excited state of the opposite parity into the ground state and a marked enhancement in the intensity of the band upon complexation is observed. This is due to an increase in the configuration interaction upon complexation¹⁴. The Pr^{III} complexes shows bands around 16500–17300, 21000–21500, 21700–22000 and 22100–23200 cm^{-1} corresponding to the transition from 3H_4 to 1D_2 , 3P_0 , 3P_1 and 3P_2 energy levels,

respectively.

The nephelauxetic effect is quantitatively described by a nephelauxetic parameter ($\bar{\beta}$) equal to the ratio of the interelectron repulsion parameter (either Slater's integrals F_k , or Racah's parameter E^k) in the complex and in the free ion :

$$\beta = \frac{(F_k)_{\text{complex}}}{(F_k)_{\text{free ion}}} \quad \text{or} \quad \bar{\beta} = \frac{(E^k)_{\text{complex}}}{(E^k)_{\text{free ion}}}$$

As the nephelauxetic effect value $(1 - \bar{\beta})$ is small in the lanthanide complex, it can be, to a fairly good approximation defined from the ratio of the wave numbers of f - f transitions in the spectra of the complex and the free ion.

$$\beta \approx \frac{V_{\text{complex}}}{V_{\text{free ion}}}$$

Since, in general case, the energy levels in the lanthanide free ions are unknown the relative nephelauxetic effects $\bar{\beta}$ and are usually determined from the experimental data using the spectra of the lanthanide aqua ions as standards.

$$\bar{\beta} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{n=1}^n \frac{V_{\text{complex}}}{V_{\text{aquo}}}$$

From the mean $\bar{\beta}$ values, Sinha's covalency parameter (δ) and bonding parameter ($b^{1/2}$) are calculated using the following formulas :

$$\delta = \frac{1 - \bar{\beta}}{\bar{\beta}} \times 100 \quad \text{and} \quad b^{1/2} = \left[\frac{1 - \bar{\beta}}{2} \right]^{1/2}$$

These parameters measure the amount of 4f-ligand mixing, i.e. covalency.

The values the parameters $\bar{\beta}$, δ and $b^{1/2}$ of these complexes in the Table 2. The values of $\bar{\beta}$ which are less than unity and the positive values of δ and $b^{1/2}$ support partial covalent nature of bonding between the metal and ligands.

Infrared spectra :

Important IR spectral bands of the Schiff bases and their corresponding lanthanum(III) and praseodymium(III) complexes are given in Table 3. The assignments of infrared spectral bands of the ligands and the complexes are based on earlier studies of similar ligands¹⁵⁻¹⁷. Organic compounds having a thioamide group ($\text{H-N-C}=\text{S}$) give rise to four thioamide bands in the infrared spectra.

Table 2. Electronic spectral bands and parameters of praseodymium(III) complexes of 4-amino-3-(phenyl/substituted-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole and 2,6-diacetylpyridine

Complex	Bands (cm ⁻¹)	Assignments	$\bar{\nu}$	δ	$b^{1/2}$	μ_{eff}
[PrCl(DPMT)H ₂ O]	16500	³ H ₄ → ¹ D ₂	0.9741	2.6584	0.1137	3.58
	21075	³ H ₄ → ³ P ₆				
	21775	³ H ₄ → ³ P ₁				
	22175	³ H ₄ → ³ P ₂				
[PrCl(DOCMT)H ₂ O]	16876	³ H ₄ → ¹ D ₂	0.9770	2.3542	0.1072	3.60
	21175	³ H ₄ → ³ P ₆				
	21800	³ H ₄ → ³ P ₁				
	22375	³ H ₄ → ³ P ₂				
[PrCl(DPCMT)H ₂ O]	17270	³ H ₄ → ¹ D ₂	0.9776	2.2918	0.1058	3.61
	21475	³ H ₄ → ³ P ₆				
	21725	³ H ₄ → ³ P ₁				
	22975	³ H ₄ → ³ P ₂				
[PrCl(DNMT)H ₂ O]	17175	³ H ₄ → ¹ D ₂	0.9875	1.2653	0.0758	3.60
	21370	³ H ₄ → ³ P ₆				
	21975	³ H ₄ → ³ P ₁				
	23200	³ H ₄ → ³ P ₂				

Table 3. IR spectral data of Schiff bases derived from 4-amino-3-(phenyl/substituted phenyl)-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole with 2,6-diacetylpyridine and their corresponding lanthanum(III) and praseodymium(III) complexes

Ligand/Complex	Data (cm ⁻¹)
[LaCl(DPMT)H ₂ O]	3325m, 3190m, 2985w, 2945w, 1610s, 1600w, 1590m, 1545s, 1500m, 1480m, 1300w, 1255m, 1160w, 1085m, 840w, 810w, 785m, 640w, 620s, 450w, 425m, 405w, 390w, 280w
[PrCl(DPMT)H ₂ O]	3360m, 3205m, 2950w, 1600s, 1585m, 1500m, 1480m, 1420m, 1320w, 1140w, 1020m, 975s, 840w, 820w, 810w, 680w, 640w, 610s, 590s, 470m, 460w, 415m, 400w, 380m, 265w
[LaCl(DOCMT)H ₂ O]	3350m, 3075m, 3015wm, 2985w, 2960w, 2860w, 1610s, 1595w, 1580m, 1510m, 1475m, 1415m, 1310w, 1150w, 1025m, 970s, 850w, 800w, 680w, 640w, 620s, 465w, 485m, 420m, 400w, 385m, 250w
[PrCl(DOCMT)H ₂ O]	3355m, 3070m, 3020m, 2980w, 2965w, 1610s, 1600w, 1590m, 1500m, 1480m, 1420m, 1300w, 1150w, 1020m, 975s, 840w, 810w, 680w, 645w, 485m, 460w, 425w, 390m, 240w
[LaCl(DPCMT)H ₂ O]	3300m, 3075m, 3015wm, 2985w, 2960w, 2860w, 1605s, 1595w, 1580m, 1510m, 1475m, 1415m, 1310w, 1150w, 1025m, 973s, 850w, 800w, 680w, 640w, 620s, 480m, 465w, 430m, 400w, 380m, 245w
[PrCl(DPCMT)H ₂ O]	3395m, 3080m, 3020m, 2970w, 2950w, 1610s, 1595w, 1580m, 1515m, 1475m, 1420m, 1310w, 1150w, 1025m, 975s, 845w, 820w, 800w, 680w, 645w, 620s, 475m, 460w, 425m, 400w, 390m, 270w
[LaCl(DNMT)H ₂ O]	3340m, 3075m, 3010m, 2975w, 2950w, 1620s, 1600w, 1580m, 1510m, 1470m, 1415m, 1305w, 1155w, 1025m, 970s, 845w, 815w, 805w, 640w, 610s, 470m, 465w, 415m, 405w, 375m
[PrCl(DNMT)H ₂ O]	3350m, 3070m, 3015m, 2970w, 2960w, 1610s, 1595w, 1582m, 1505m, 1465m, 1410m, 1310w, 1150w, 1020m, 810w, 810w, 640w, 620w, 475m, 460w, 420m, 402w, 390m, 275w

The thioamide bands are -I at ~1520 cm⁻¹, band -II at ~1400-1300 cm⁻¹, band -III at ~1000 cm⁻¹ and band -IV at ~850-700 cm⁻¹. These bands have contributions from $\delta(\text{C-H}) + \delta(\text{N-H})$, $\nu(\text{C=S}) + \nu(\text{C=N}) + \delta(\text{C-H})$, $\nu(\text{C-N}) +$ respectively. In the present ligands, these bands appear in the range *ca.* 1530-1510, 1320-1280, 1060-1040 and 820-780 cm⁻¹. The bands are expected^{18,19} to be affected differently by different modes of coordination. It has been suggested that the coordina-

tion of amido nitrogen is accompanied by a small increase in the thioamide -I band. The coordination through the thio-keto sulphur causes the decreases in the frequency of the thioamide -IV band. However, in the complexes cited in this section, all thioamide bands disappear indicating that mixing of $\nu(\text{C-N})$, $\delta(\text{N-H})$ and $\nu(\text{C=S})$ vibrations may be absent. In addition, a weak band at *ca.* 2480 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of ligands (in solution) due to the -SH group vibration further suggests the thione \rightleftharpoons

thiol tautomerism. However, in the complexes this band disappears indicating the coordination through sulphur after deprotonation. The infrared spectra of the complexes show a band at *ca.* 620 cm^{-1} which is due to conversion of C=S to C-S. The (Ln-S) vibration²⁰ appears at *ca.* 390–375 cm^{-1} .

The bands observed around 1640–1620, 1590–1570 and 1500 cm^{-1} in the spectra of the ligands may be assigned¹⁹ to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$, $(\text{N}=\text{N}=\text{C}-)$, $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ ring and $\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$ (phenyl) vibrations, respectively. Strong vibrations in the region 1600–1550 cm^{-1} are usually associated with phenyl and C=N groups and it is normally not possible to identify such bands with particular C=C or C=N linkage. However, a stringent assignment of C=N group can be made by comparing the spectrum of the parent mercapto triazole containing N-NH₂ group with that of the ligands in which N-NH₂ group is replaced by N-N=CH group. Following this method, the strong band observed at 1640–1620 cm^{-1} is assigned to the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ vibration. The spectra of the complexes show the shifting of this band to lower frequency ($\sim 20 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) indicating the coordination of the azomethine nitrogen to the metal atom. The bands observed at 430–415 cm^{-1} may be assigned to $\nu(\text{Ln}-\text{N})$ ²⁰.

The pyridine ring deformation at *ca.* 1590 cm^{-1} (8a), in-plane ring deformation at *ca.* 690 cm^{-1} (6a) and out-of-plane ring deformation at 450 cm^{-1} (16b) in ligands appear around 1600, 640 and 465 cm^{-1} in complexes. The shift in these frequencies indicates the coordination of the pyridine nitrogen to the metal atom^{21–25}.

The complexes show medium intensity band at about 3360–3320 cm^{-1} which may be due to $\nu(\text{O}-\text{H})$ of water molecules.

Thus, the infrared spectra reveal that the ligands LH₂ act as tetradentate, dibasic chelating agents having coordination sites at thiol sulphur atoms and azomethine

nitrogens.

Proton magnetic resonance spectra :

The proton magnetic resonance spectra of lanthanum(III) complexes, [LaCl(L)(H₂O)] have been recorded in deuterated dimethylsulphoxide. The different proton magnetic resonance signals are given in Table 4. The intensities of all the resonance lines were determined by planimetric integration. The spectra are complicated by coupling between various groups but a comparison of the spectra of ligands with those of the complexes can lead to the following conclusions :

- A signal appears at *ca.* δ 8.5 in the spectra of all ligands due to (S-H) group indicating that ligands exist in thiol form in solution. The signal disappears in all complexes indicating deprotonation of the thiol group.
- All ligands give signal at *ca.* δ 7.1–7.3 integrating for aromatic group protons. The signal shows slight shift upon coordination.
- The signal due to -CH=N appear at *ca.* δ 8.2 in the spectra of ligands and complexes.
- A singlet appears at *ca.* δ 2.20–2.25 due to -CH₃ group.
- The proton signal due to coordinated water molecule appears at *ca.* δ 5.45.
- The ligands show two signals in the range δ 7.50–7.65 and δ 7.72–7.82 due to pyridine ring. These signals shift slightly downfield in the complexes which may be due to coordination of pyridine nitrogen to metal.

X-Ray powder diffraction pattern :

X-Ray powder diffraction pattern of one representative complex [LaCl(DPMT)H₂O] is shown in Fig. 1. The structural characterization of the complex was carried out from the analysis of X-ray powder diffraction (XRD)

Table 4. ¹H NMR data (δ scale, ppm) of lanthanum(III) complexes with Schiff bases derived from 4-amino-3-(phenyl/substituted phenyl)-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles and 2,6-diacetylpyrid

Compd.	Aromatic ring	Pyridine ring	H ₂ O	-CH ₃
[LaCl(DPMT)H ₂ O]	7.20–7.38m	7.68(t), 7.85(d)	5.40s	2.20s
[LaCl(DOCMT)H ₂ O]	7.15–7.32m	7.65(t), 7.80(d)	5.42s	2.25s
[LaCl(DPCMT)H ₂ O]	7.10–7.20m	7.62(t), 7.78(d)	5.45s	2.18s
[LaCl(DNMT)H ₂ O]	7.22–7.30m	7.70(t), 7.84(d)	5.48s	2.22s

Fig. 1. XRD of [LaCl(DPMT)H₂O] complex.

patterns obtained using an X-ray powder diffractometer (Bruker AXS D8 Advance) with CuK α_1 ($\lambda = 1.54056$ Å) source. The XRD patterns of the complex were given in Table 5. The peaks in the XRD pattern clearly indicate the formation of nanocrystals. The crystallite sizes have been calculated using Debye-Scherrer formula^{26,27} given by,

$$D = 0.94 \lambda / \beta \cos \theta$$

where D is the crystallite size, λ is the wavelength of X-ray used; β is the full width at half maximum (FWHM)

and is the Bragg angle of diffraction. The average crystallite size of the complex was found to be 25.17 nm.

The indexing of the powder patterns for each complex was carried out using the program N-TREOR. The Miller indices (hkl) relate the peak positions or d -spacings to the lattice parameters by an equation specific to the crystal system. The initial unit cell (lattice) parameters were also determined by N-TREOR²⁸. These unit cell parameters were refined from the regression analysis and the best crystal system and space group were assigned using CHEKCELL²⁹ program. It was found that the complex

Table 5. The unit cell parameters and observed and calculated X-Ray diffraction data for [LaCl(DPMT)H₂O] complex

$a = 20.6421 \text{ \AA}, b = 26.8436 \text{ \AA}, c = 5.4775 \text{ \AA}, \beta = 91.63^\circ, \text{ Cell vol.} = 3033.85 \text{ \AA}^3$

Sr. No.	d (obs)	D (calc)	Δ (d)	$I/I_m \times 100$	2θ (obs)	2θ (calc)	Δ (2θ)	h	k	l
1.	3.2775	3.2718	0.0057	16.78	27.186	27.234	-0.048	-5	5	0
2.	2.8356	2.8369	-0.0013	100.00	31.525	31.510	0.015	-5	5	1
3.	2.6929	2.6902	0.0027	21.08	33.242	33.277	-0.035	1	1	2
4.	2.5916	2.5939	-0.0023	8.36	34.582	34.550	0.032	1	9	1
5.	2.4883	2.4863	0.0020	7.65	36.065	36.097	-0.032	4	8	1
6.	2.3865	2.3901	-0.0036	20.53	37.661	37.602	0.059	4	0	2
7.	2.2528	2.2516	0.0012	11.40	39.988	40.011	-0.023	4	4	2
8.	2.1919	2.1942	-0.0023	6.23	41.149	41.104	0.045	-4	10	1
9.	2.0752	2.0766	-0.0014	5.63	43.578	43.547	0.031	5	5	2
10.	2.0043	2.0032	0.0011	74.92	45.203	45.229	-0.026	1	9	2
11.	1.6337	1.6332	0.0005	15.62	56.265	56.281	-0.016	4	12	2
12.	1.4142	1.4141	0.0001	3.17	66.007	66.010	-0.003	0	12	3
13.	1.2631	1.2630	0.0001	14.29	75.161	75.161	-0.001	-9	15	2

Table 6. Fungitoxic screening data of lanthanum(III) and praseodymium(III) complexes with Schiff bases derived from 4-amino-3-(phenyl/substituted phenyl)-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles and 2,6-diacetylpyridine

Compd.	Fungicidal inhibition (%); Compound dose (ppm)								
	<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i>			<i>Curvularia lunata</i>			<i>Colletotrichum falcatum</i>		
	10	100	1000	10	100	1000	10	100	1000
[LaCl(DPMT)H ₂ O]	50.0	67.4	71.9	54.6	62.8	72.8	59.4	69.2	71.9
[PrCl(DPMT)H ₂ O]	52.5	62.1	74.1	56.7	67.2	73.2	56.4	64.1	73.1
[LaCl(DOCMT)H ₂ O]	51.9	65.4	75.8	54.1	65.0	74.1	56.0	66.9	72.4
[PrCl(DOCMT)H ₂ O]	50.8	62.2	73.4	54.4	68.8	72.0	51.2	62.4	75.2
[LaCl(DPCMT)H ₂ O]	53.8	64.6	79.8	53.3	67.5	76.5	55.5	62.6	77.2
[PrCl(DPCMT)H ₂ O]	50.7	61.3	72.8	55.2	65.0	75.3	54.6	66.9	76.5
[LaCl(DNMT)H ₂ O]	54.2	68.0	75.2	52.6	62.8	74.9	54.8	65.2	73.8
[PrCl(DNMT)H ₂ O]	52.1	64.9	76.2	51.2	60.5	79.2	52.0	63.2	78.0
Fluconazole	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100

reveals monoclinic crystal system with the most probable space group C2/c. The lattice parameters and observed and calculated X-ray diffraction data for the complex has been shown in Table 5.

Antifungal activity :

Activities of the complexes in Table 6 reveal that the activity of the complexes is affected by the nature of substituent(s) and donor site of the ligands, this in relation to their membrane permeability, a key factor in determining their entry inside the cell. In Table 6, activities of the complexes with respect to different fungi at different concentrations have been compared with standard drug fluconazole. All complexes show slightly higher activity as compared to free ligands to other fungi.

Fig. 2. Graph showing the inhibition percentage of synthesized compounds against fungus species.

Fig. 3. Thermal behaviour of complex through TGA techniques.

The toxicity of compounds is directly proportional to the concentration. The most active complexes against different fungi at 1000 ppm concentrations have also been compared and illustrated in Fig. 2.

Conclusions

Thus, on the basis of elemental analyses, electrical conductance measurements and spectral data, the following structure is tentatively proposed for $[\text{LnCl}(\text{L})(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$ complexes.

The fungicidal screening of the complexes led to the conclusions that metal complexes are more active than the free ligand.

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